

Design of a Linear Transconductance OTA using the Open Sky130 Process Design Kit

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Abstract—This paper describes the design, layout and simulation of a linear transconductance Operational Transconductance Amplifier (OTA) using the SkyWater 130 nm open Process Design Kit (PDK). By using a known source degeneration technique, it is possible to either decrease and linearize the transconductance of the OTA for a wider range of input voltages, making it proper for use on Gm-C filters. Only open source tools, suited for the Sky130 PDK, were used in this design, showing the applicability to analog designs.

Index Terms—OTA, linear transconductance, open PDKs, Sky130, open source tools.

I. INTRODUCTION

The Gm-C filters can be used in a great variety of applications as, for example, in disk drive read channels [1], anti-aliasing filters [2], wireless communications [3] and even in biomedical circuits [4]. It is interesting to note that these applications spread over a wide range of frequencies. The basic building block of these filters are the Gm-C integrator, composed by an operational transconductance amplifier (OTA) and a capacitor, as described in [5].

In [6], a bank of high-order passband Gm-C filters was proposed, devised to be used in a power quality measurement system. The bank is composed by ten 16th-order passband filters with a band of 15 kHz each, ranging from 2 kHz to 150 kHz. The aim of the filter bank is to measure the supraharmonic components superimposed to the line ac voltage. In that work, all simulations were done using a simplified OTA model, composed simply by a voltage-controlled current source and an output resistance. In a later work [7], simulation results were shown for a filter bank designed at transistor level, using BSIM predictive models, available in [8]. However, the OTAs and consequently the filters were not laid out.

That design revealed the need of OTAs with transconductances with several order of magnitudes, ranging from order of 10^{-7} to 10^{-3} ampères per volts (A/V). Some techniques for obtaining low transconductance OTAs are presented in [9]. Moreover, for a power quality measurement system, it is important to keep the OTAs responses linear over a wide range of input voltages. The source-degenerating scheme can

provide a linear response over a wide differential input range, and was used for the design of the OTAs in [10].

The launching of the SkyWater open process design kit (PDK) in 2020 [11] filled a lack in the design of chips, especially for undergraduate students. Supported by Google, some runs were promoted for fabrication of selected projects using the process hereafter named Sky130, which is a hybrid, 130 nm, 1.8-V CMOS process. Although the majority of projects using the Sky130 PDK are currently for digital circuits, several analog projects have already been published, as in [12] and [13]. The PDK was released for use with free and open-source tools, some of them totally adapted for the Sky130 process.

This paper describes the design of a linear transconductance OTA using the source-degeneration scheme, employing the Sky130 PDK. Only open source tools were used for simulation, layout and extraction. The objective of this work is to show a guideline for those who want to start with the PDK for analog design. Simulation results will be shown for two different source-degeneration approaches.

The work is organized as follows: in Section II, the OTA structure and the design methodology is briefly described. In Section III, the layout is commented. In Section IV, simulation results for both extracted netlists are discussed. Finally, the conclusions are presented in Section V.

II. OTA STRUCTURE

The proposed topology for the OTA is based on the source-degeneration scheme, that can linearize the OTA response and either reduce its transconductance gain, if compared to the basic OTA [10]. The circuit is depicted in Fig. 1. Each transistor of the differential pair (M_1 and M_2) is biased by currents that are replica of I_B (which flows into M_B), imposed by transistors M_3 and M_4 , respectively. Two resistors R_{s1} and R_{s2} are then placed among the sources of M_1 and M_2 . The choice of two resistors instead of just one has the objective of give more flexibility to the layout.

The resistors can be replaced by MOSFETs in triode region, as depicted in detail in Fig. 3b, acting as voltage-controlled resistors (in this case, with gate voltage set to $V_{DD} = 1.8$ V).

Fig. 2. OTA layout, with identification of some relevant parts: (A) differential pair; (B) source-degeneration resistors; (C) biasing transistors.

Fig. 1(b). The aspect ratios of these components were obtained after a .OP simulation, to give their conductances g_{ds} equal to $1/R_{s1,s2}$. The Table I shows all the aspect ratios (W/L) of the components.

III. CIRCUIT LAYOUT

The layout of the OTA was done by using two open source tools: Magic VLSI Layout Tool, an EDA software written in 1980s, re-suited for use with the Sky130 PDK; and KLayout, a more modern open source layout tool. The advantage of using Magic is the possibility of automatic generation of the circuit components (in this case, low-Vt PMOS and NMOS, and XRES poly resistors). Moreover, Magic is efficient for design rule checking (DRC) and circuit extraction.

However, considering that Magic has a poor handling interface, if compared with modern tools, the following design methodology was adopted: (i) generation of the devices in Magic, upon the dimensions contained in Table I, and exporting of the devices for GDSII format; (ii) importing of the GDSII file in KLayout, where all connections with metal layers were done; (iii) DRC in KLayout, using the package available in [15]; (iv) importing of the GDSII in Magic, for circuit extraction.

By using this strategy, it was possible to create the layout shown in Fig. 2, which emphasizes the differential pair (A), the source degeneration resistors (B) and the biasing transistors (C). The layout with source-degenerating MOSFETs has a similar aspect, just replacing the elements in (B), since the sizes of the MOSFETs occupy an area slightly lower than the high resistance resistors, for this design.

The total area of the block is $1820 \mu m^2$ ($35 \mu m \times 52 \mu m$). For this design, the area optimization was not prioritized, since the main objective was to test the design tools with the Sky130 PDK. The transistors and resistors, for example, were placed with individual guard rings, generated automatically by Magic, which use an additional area. For the PMOS devices, this means individual N-wells for each transistor. The metal widths and spacing between devices were also larger than the minimum allowable by the design rules.

IV. SIMULATION RESULTS

The layout of Fig. 2 was extracted for post-layout simulation with the open tool NGSPICE. For evaluation of the improvement in the linearity of the source-degeneration scheme, two simulation strategies are shown: (i) the transconductance plot versus differential input voltage; (ii) a DC sweep, plotting the output current versus the differential input voltage. For comparison, results for the circuit with source-degeneration resistors are shown with results for the circuits with triode source-degeneration MOSFETs.

For all circuits, $V_{DD} = 1.8$ V, and $V_{CM} = 0.9$ V, where V_{CM} is the common-mode voltage.

For evaluating the transconductance, a step .AC analysis was applied at a fixed frequency (1 kHz), varying the DC differential voltage applied at the inputs of the differential pair, producing the plot shown in Fig. 3. It can be shown that a transconductance close to $21 \mu A/V$ is approximately maintained over a range of about ± 0.59 V, evidencing the feature of the structure in obtaining a quasi-linear response for a larger range of the input signal.

The DC sweep was performed by varying the differential input voltage, resulting in the plot shown in Fig. 4. Again, it shows a practically linear response in the range of ± 0.59 V.

From the transconductance plots, it can be seen that the response for the circuit with the resistors exhibits little difference if compared with that obtained for the circuit with triode MOSFETs. However, since the g_{ds} conductances of the MOSFETs are determined by $(V_{GS} - V_t)$, where, in this case, $V_{GS} = V_{DD}$, then the sensitivity of the circuit with triode MOSFETs to supply variations is considerably higher than that obtained for the source resistors.

V. CONCLUSION

This paper presented the design of an OTA with linearized transconductance over a wide range of differential input voltage. It is a useful block in designing Gm-C filters.

As design example, an OTA with $21 \mu A/V$ was considered. The source-degeneration scheme was adopted, in order to either linearize and also reduce the transconductance, which

Fig. 3. Plotting of the transconductance versus input voltage, for the two approaches. Red: using resistors; Black: using triode MOSFETs.

Fig. 4. Plotting of the DC sweep for the output current. Red: using resistors; Green: using triode MOSFETs.

can be important in design of low-frequency filters. However, the technique can be used in the design of linearized OTAs with transconductances of other orders of magnitude.

Although the topology itself does not present a novelty in analog circuit design, the use of the Sky130 open PDK and the employment of open source tools suited for this design kit were the differential aspects of this work.

Post-layout simulation results obtained with NGSPICE demonstrated that the purpose of achieving a linear transconductance over a wide range of input voltages was achieved, both for the circuit using resistors or using triode MOSFETs as source-degenerating elements.

The analysis of the circuit considering mismatching models of the devices is considered for future works, as well as the adaptation of this circuit to a fully differential version. In this case, a common-mode feedback circuit will be needed.

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REFERENCES

- [1] C. A. Laber and P. R. Gray, "A 20-MHz Sixth-Order BiCMOS Parasitic-Insensitive Continuous-Time Filter and Second-Order Equalizer Optimized for Disk-Drive Read Channels," *IEEE Journal of Solid-State Circuits*, vol. 28, no. 4, pp. 462-470, April 1993.
- [2] R. F. L. Moreno, "Filtro Anti-aliasing gm-C totalmente diferencial e sintonizável", final paper (in portuguese). Escola Politécnica da Universidade Federal do Rio de Janeiro, June 2009.
- [3] G. Eason, B. Noble, and I. N. Sneddon, "On certain integrals of Lipschitz-Hankel type involving products of Bessel functions," *Phil. Trans. Roy. Soc. London*, vol. A247, pp. 529-551, April 1955.
- [4] L. J. Stotts, "Introduction to Implantable Biomedical IC Design," *IEEE Circuits and Devices Magazine*, pp. 12-18, January 1989.

- [5] Y. P. Tsvividis, "Integrated Continuous-Time Filter Design - An Overview," *IEEE Journal of Solid-State Circuits*, vol. 29, no. 3, pp. 166-176, March 1994.
- [6] M. X. Ferreira, T. M. Mendes, L. R. M. Silva, E. C. Teixeira, C. A. Duque, "A Gm-C Filter Bank for Supraharmonic Analysis Application". In: 20th Microelectronics Student Forum (SForum 2020) - Chip in the Fields, virtual event, 2020.
- [7] M. J. P. Cunha, A. B. Moreira, M. X. Ferreira and E. C. Teixeira, "Design and Transistor-Level Simulation of a High- Order Gm-C Filter Bank." In: 22nd Microelectronics Student Forum (SForum 2022) - Chip in Minuano, virtual event, 2022.
- [8] Predictive Technology Model, Latest models. Available at: <https://ptm.asu.edu/>. Access 10 June 2023.
- [9] A. Veeravalli, E. Sánchez-Sinencio, J. Silva-Martínez, "Transconductance amplifier structures with very small transconductances: a comparative design approach". *IEEE Journal of Solid-state Circuits*, v. 37, n. 6, pp. 770-775, 2002.
- [10] K. Garradhi, N. Hassen, K. Besbes, "Low-Voltage and Low-Power OTA Using Source-Degeneration Technique and Its Application in Gm-C Filter". In: 2016 11th International Design & Test Symposium (IDT), pp. 221-226, 2016.
- [11] Skywater Open Source PDK. Available at: <https://github.com/google/skywater-pdk>. Access 08 June 2023.
- [12] A. Pajkanovic, "Open Source CMOS General Purpose Operational Amplifier". In: Proc. 2021 IEEE 32nd International Conference on Microelectronics (MIEL), Niš, Serbia, 2021.
- [13] W. M. M. Oliveira, F. Brito-Filho, "Development of a Baseband Amplifier for a 130 nm CMOS process using open-source design flow". In: International Symposium on Instrumentation Systems, Circuits and Transducers - INSCIT 2022 - Chip in Minuano, virtual event, Brazil, 2022.
- [14] SkyWater SKY130 PDK, Device Details. Available at: <https://skywater-pdk.readthedocs.io/en/main/rules/device-details.html>. Access June 12, 2023.
- [15] Sky130 for KLayout. Available at: https://github.com/laurentc2/SKY130_for_KLayout. Access 10 June 2023.